

Synthesis, characterization and *in vivo* anthelmintic activity of some newer piperazine derivatives

Devender Pathak*, Suman Lata Pandey and Nitin Kumar

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Rajiv Academy for Pharmacy, Mathura, N.H. #2 Delhi-Mathura Bye-pass, P.O. Chhatikara, Mathura-281 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dev_15@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Substituted primary aromatic amines on diazotization gives diazonium salt which on reaction with various piperazine derivatives get converted into diazotized product 3a-e, 4a-e and 5b-c. The structures of the newly synthesized piperazine derivatives were accomplished through IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. All derivatives showed moderate to good anthelmintic activity against *Phaeritima posthuma* species of earthworm at the concentration of 75.0 mg/mL, when compared with piperazine citrate as reference compound. Among all the synthesized compounds, the compound 2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-1-phenyldiazene (4a), 2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)diazene (4b) and 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)diazene (4c) were found to be most potent towards anthelmintic activity.

Keywords : Diazotization, piperazine, anthelmintic activity.

Introduction

Piperazine derivatives have been extensively investigated by the organic chemists due to their close association with various types of biological activities. Moreover they have wide clinical applications in the therapy of functional diseases and exhibit anthelmintic, antibacterial and insecticidal activities. The synthesis of piperazine and its derivatives has received growing interest because of their potent applications in the drugs, perfumery and pharmaceutical industries^{1,2}. Nitrogen in piperazine ring plays an important role in biological research and drug manufacturing industry including the preparation of anthelmintic^{3,4}, anti-allergic⁵, antibacterial⁶, antihistaminic⁷, antiemetic^{8,9} and antimigraine agents¹⁰. Helminth infections are among the most common infections in man, affecting a large proportion of the world's population. Piperazine is used as a main ingredient of anthelmintic drugs used to treat intestinal roundworm (ascariasis) infection in human and poultry and to treat pinworms (enterobiasis; oxyuriasis) by altering cell membrane permeability and causing hyperpolarization of the membrane¹¹⁻¹³ which causes paralysis and death of the individual worm^{14,15}. Various substitution can be made on piperazine nucleus to enhance the activity. Substitution at 4th position in

piperazine nucleus, make it more potent toward anthelmintic activity¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

This study focused on the synthesis of some newer piperazine derivatives through diazotization reaction and their significant role in anthelmintic activity.

Results and discussion

Substituted primary aromatic amines were reacted with piperazine derivatives, followed by diazotization reaction at 0-5 °C, as shown in Scheme 1. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds 3a-e, 4a-e, 5b-c were established through elemental analysis, m.p. determination and spectral (FTIR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopy) studies. In IR spectra of series, significant bands were appeared at 3348 (N-H), 3050 (aromatic C-H), 1589 (N=N), 1311 (aromatic C-N), 1188 (N-CH₃), 1170 cm⁻¹ (N-C₂H₅). In ¹H NMR spectra of these compounds a singlet for NH in various derivatives appeared between δ 1.00-2.00 ppm and a multiplet of 8 proton of piperazine appeared between δ 2.00-4.00 ppm. Broad multiplet of aromatic proton appeared between δ 7.00-8.00 ppm. All derivatives showed peaks at M+1 in their mass spectra.

The piperazine ring is of fundamental importance for anthelmintic activity, as it blocks the GABA (γ-amino

butyric acid) receptor. Association of ring moiety (piperazine) with center which is cationic (azo group in the series) at physiological pH values confers anthelmintic properties on molecules. The attachment of phenyl ring to N=N (diazo group) seemed necessary for anthelmintic activity. The activity was found to be most marked in *p*-Cl and *p*-NO₂ substitution.

Anthelmintic activity :

Anthelmintic activity was evaluated on earthworm, *Phaeritima posthuma*. Earthworms were divided into fourteen groups (5 each). The first group served as normal control which received Tween-80 (0.5%) and distilled water only, second group received the standard drug i.e. Piperazine citrate in Tween-80 (0.5%), distilled water and a dose level of 75.0 mg/mL and other test groups received various doses of synthesized compounds in Tween-80 (0.5%) and distilled water. Observations were made for the time taken to cause paralysis and death of individual worms for two hours. The paralyzing and death times were noted and their mean was calculated for triplicate sets. The results of anthelmintic activity are shown in Table 1. It was concluded that among all the synthesized compounds : 2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-1-phenyldiazene (**4a**), 2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)diazene (**4b**) and 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)diazene (**4c**) showed potent anthelmintic activity against *Phaeritima posthuma* species of earthworm, compared to standard drug piperazine citrate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were procured from Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai and Central Drug House (P.) Ltd., New Delhi. All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates was used to access the reactions and purity of synthesized compounds. Satisfactory C, H, N analyses were obtained for all the compounds on a Carlo Erba EA 1108 elemental analyzer. The λ_{\max} of the synthesized compounds were scanned on UV-Visible Spectrophotometer Pharma spec-1700 (Shimadzu). IR spectrum of compounds in KBr pellets were recorded on a FTIR-8400 S spectrophotometer (Shimadzu). ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds were

Table 1. Anthelmintic activity of compounds

Compd.	Compd. conc. (mg/mL)	<i>Phaeritima posthuma</i>	
		Mean paralyzing time (min)	Mean death time (min)
3a	37.5	52.22 ± 0.81	57.66 ± 0.47
	75.0	41.66 ± 0.47	51.00 ± 0.81
	150.0	34.33 ± 0.94	42.00 ± 0.81
3b	37.5	59.33 ± 0.40	69.66 ± 0.40
	75.0	52.33 ± 0.48	62.33 ± 0.52
	150.0	42.33 ± 0.26	57.33 ± 0.44
3c	37.5	27.66 ± 0.48	43.33 ± 0.56
	75.0	22.66 ± 0.32	36.33 ± 0.56
	150.0	19.66 ± 0.29	27.33 ± 0.45
3d	37.5	57.67 ± 0.90	78.30 ± 0.87
	75.0	44.60 ± 0.30	57.38 ± 0.48
	150.0	33.38 ± 0.78	36.32 ± 0.86
3e	37.5	51.33 ± 0.35	59.33 ± 0.80
	75.0	49.33 ± 0.48	57.33 ± 0.29
	150.0	42.33 ± 0.91	50.66 ± 0.32
4a	37.5	15.33 ± 0.52	24.66 ± 0.33
	75.0	13.66 ± 0.70	21.33 ± 0.64
	150.0	11.66 ± 0.34	19.33 ± 0.40
4b	37.5	27.66 ± 0.48	42.33 ± 0.48
	75.0	21.33 ± 0.60	36.33 ± 0.66
	150.0	19.33 ± 0.81	29.33 ± 0.38
4c	37.5	15.33 ± 0.49	18.66 ± 0.75
	75.0	14.33 ± 0.35	17.66 ± 0.43
	150.0	10.33 ± 0.41	16.33 ± 0.29
4d	37.5	50.13 ± 0.28	78.32 ± 0.87
	5.0	41.60 ± 0.77	57.38 ± 0.48
	150.0	29.19 ± 0.83	36.32 ± 0.86
4e	37.5	62.66 ± 0.75	78.66 ± 0.42
	75.0	53.33 ± 0.64	64.66 ± 0.92
	150.0	40.66 ± 0.29	51.33 ± 0.85
5b	37.5	59.33 ± 0.32	67.66 ± 0.59
	75.0	46.66 ± 0.65	57.33 ± 0.61
	150.0	37.33 ± 0.81	47.33 ± 0.89
5c	37.5	59.33 ± 0.40	69.66 ± 0.40
	75.0	48.66 ± 0.83	57.66 ± 0.89
	150.0	38.33 ± 0.39	48.33 ± 0.39
Piperazine citrate (standard)	75.0	28.66 ± 0.82	34.66 ± 0.79
Control	-	-	-

Data are given as mean ± S.D. (n = 3); S.D. = standard deviation.

recorded on Bruker NMR spectrophotometer in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were obtained on a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

Scheme 1

General procedure for the synthesis of 1-(substitutedphenyl)-2-(substitutedpiperazin-1-yl)diazene (3a-e)(4a-e)(5b-c) : A mixture of aniline derivatives (0.01 mol), 8 mL of distilled water and concentrated hydrochloric acid (8 mL) was warmed on water bath to make clear solution. Then the mixture was stirred for 1 h maintaining the temperature (0–5 °C), followed by the addition of sodium nitrite solution until the red litmus turns blue (pH 7.0–8.0) (Diazotization process). After completion of diazotization a solution of substituted piperazine (0.01 mol) in sodium hydroxide (20% w/v) was added. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained between 7.0–8.0 by adding sodium carbonate solution (10% w/v).

The resulting solution was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to give a solid compound.

Spectral analysis :

3a : Yield : 1.18 g, 69%, m.p. 109–110 °C (Found : C, 63.12; H, 7.41; N, 29.44. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₄N₄ : C, 63.13; H, 7.42; N, 29.45%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 313.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3328 (N–H stretching, 2°amine), 3093.61 (aromatic C–H stretching), 3062 (aliphatic C–H stretching), 1581 (N=N stretching), 1561.94 (aromatic C=C stretching), 1333 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C–N stretching); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 2.09 (1H, s, N–H, D₂O exchangeable), 3.33–3.46 (4H, m, N–CH), 3.81–4.35

(4H, m, N-CH₂), 6.87 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.20–7.38 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 205(100) [M+1]⁺, 192(72), 177(41), 162(18), 133(24), 113(16), 105(86), 99(23), 77(52).

3b : Yield : 1.18 g, 64%, m.p. 159–160 °C (Found : C, 48.84; H, 5.02; N, 31.62. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃N₅O₂ : C, 48.86; H, 5.01; N, 31.66%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 356.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3347 (N–H stretching, 2°amine), 3105 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1627 (N=N stretching), 1595 (C=C ring stretching), 1512 (aryl N–O stretching, asym.), 1342 (aryl N–O stretching, sym.), 1330 (aromatic C–N stretching), 877 cm⁻¹ (aryl C–NO stretching); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 1.84 (1H, s, N–H, D₂O exchangeable), 3.96–3.99 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 4.19–4.21 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.58–7.67 (2H, m, Ar–H), 8.22–8.27 (2H, m, Ar–H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 235(60) [M]⁺, 236(100) [M+1]⁺, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

3c : Yield : 1.06 g, 68%, m.p. 160–161 °C (Found : C, 53.44; H, 5.81; Cl, 15.77; N, 24.93. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃ClN₄ : C, 53.45; H, 5.83; Cl, 15.78; N, 24.94%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 274.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3338 (N–H stretching, 2°amine), 3064 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1625 (N=N stretching), 1591 (C=C ring stretching), 1292 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1092 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C–Cl stretching); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 1.92 (1H, s, N–H, D₂O exchangeable), 3.38–3.44 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.68–4.03 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.33–7.44 (4H, m, Ar–H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 225(60) [M+1]⁺, 226(20) [M+2]⁺, 192(74), 162(18), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

3d : Yield : 1.05 g, 59%, m.p. 39–40 °C (Found : C, 44.62; H, 4.88; Br, 29.67; N, 20.80. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃BrN₄ : C, 44.63; H, 4.87; Br, 29.69; N, 20.82%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 335.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3323 (N–H stretching, 2°amine), 3058 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1593 (N=N stretching), 1591 (C=C ring stretching), 1313 (aromatic C–N stretching), 590 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C–Br stretching); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 1.89 (1H, s, N–H, D₂O exchangeable), 3.38–3.44 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.91–4.50 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.33–7.44 (4H, m, Ar–H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 268(100) [M+1]⁺,

270(97) [M+1]⁺, 271(12) [M+2]⁺, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 139(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

3e : Yield : 1.02 g, 69%, m.p. 93–94 °C (Found : C, 62.03; H, 6.96; N, 24.13. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₆N₄O : C, 62.05; H, 6.94; N, 24.12%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 344.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3354 (N–H stretching, 2°amine), 3095 (aromatic C–H stretching), 2935 (methyl C–H stretching), 2890 (methyl C–H stretching), 1598 (N=N stretching), 1562 (C=C ring stretching), 1293 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1238 (C–O–C stretching, sym.), 1066 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C stretching, asym.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 1.34 (1H, s, N–H, D₂O exchangeable), 2.34 (3H, s, CO–CH₃), 3.16–3.18 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.91–3.94 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.51–7.59 (2H, m, Ar–H), 8.15–8.26 (2H, m, Ar–H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 232(100) [M]⁺, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 139(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

4a : Yield : 1.38 g, 73%, m.p. 49–51 °C (Found : C, 64.69; H, 7.88; N, 27.41. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₆N₄ : C, 64.68; H, 7.89; N, 27.43%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 287.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3018 (aromatic C–H stretching), 3012 (aliphatic C–H stretching), 1591 (N=N stretching), 1550 (C=C ring stretching), 1311 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1188 cm⁻¹ (C–N stretching in N–CH₃, 2°amine); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 2.06 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 3.44–3.49 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.68–3.98 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.30–7.80 (4H, m, Ar–H), 7.14 (1H, s, Ar–H); MS (ESI) *m/z* [% rel. abundance] : 205(100) [M+1]⁺, 192(72), 177(41), 162(18), 133(24), 113(16), 105(86), 99(23), 77(52).

4b : Yield : 1.06 g, 70.3%, m.p. 139–140 °C (Found : C, 53.01; H, 6.08; N, 28.12; O, 12.86. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₅N₅O₂ : C, 53.00; H, 6.07; N, 28.10; O, 12.84%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 372.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 2997 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1588 (N=N stretching), 1512 (C=C ring stretching), 150.05 (aromatic N–O stretching, asym.), 1337 (aromatic N–O stretching, sym.), 1280 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1253 (C–N stretching in N–CH₃, 3°amine), 861 cm⁻¹ (aryl C–NO stretching); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 2.04 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 3.54–3.59 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.91–3.93 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.50–

7.53 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.16–8.20 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 250(100) $[M+1]^+$, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

4c : Yield : 1.26 g, 75.0%, m.p. 59–60 °C (Found : C, 55.34; H, 6.33; Cl, 14.85; N, 23.47. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{15}ClN_4$: C, 55.34; H, 6.33; Cl, 14.85; N, 23.47%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 289.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3095 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1591 (N=N stretching), 1589 (C=C ring stretching), 1325 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1188 (C–N stretching in N–CH₃, 3°amine), 1091 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–Cl stretching); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 2.07 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 3.46–3.508 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.55–4.02 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.16–7.68 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 238(11) $[M]^+$, 239(15) $[M+1]^+$, 240(13) $[M+2]^+$, 211(35), 192(72), 177(31), 162(21), 140(37), 133(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86).

4d : Yield : 1.12 g, 62%, m.p. 180–181 °C (Found : C, 46.68; H, 5.35; Br, 28.23; N, 19.78. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{15}BrN_4$: C, 46.66; H, 5.34; Br, 28.22; N, 19.79%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 352.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3042 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1561 (C=C ring stretching), 1551 (N=N stretching), 1315 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1154 (C–N stretching, 3°amine), 582 cm^{-1} (aryl C–Br stretching); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 2.04 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 3.38–3.44 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.72–4.04 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.35–7.45 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 284(98) $[M+1]^+$, 283(12) $[M]^+$, 282(100) $[M-1]^+$, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 139(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

4e : Yield : 1.12 g, 72%, m.p. 62–63 °C (Found : C, 63.38; H, 7.39; N, 22.79. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{18}N_4O$: C, 63.39; H, 7.37; N, 22.75%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 368.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3076 (aromatic C–H stretching), 2948 (methyl C–H stretching), 2849 (methyl C–H stretching), 1578 (N=N stretching), 1558 (C=C ring stretching), 1248 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1235 (C–N stretching, 3°amine), 1225 (C–O–C stretching, sym.), 1064 cm^{-1} (C–O–C stretching, asym.); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 1.41 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 2.34 (3H, s, CO–CH₃), 3.16–3.18 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.91–3.94 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.51–7.59 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.15–8.26 (2H, m, Ar-H);

MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 246(100) $[M]^+$, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 139(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

5b : Yield : 1.16 g, 67%, m.p. 61–62 °C (Found : C, 54.76; H, 6.54; N, 26.59. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{17}N_5O_2$: C, 54.74; H, 6.51; N, 26.60%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 389.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3062 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1598 (N=N stretching), 1539 (aromatic N–O stretching, asym.), 150.06 (C=C ring stretching), 1307 (aromatic N–O stretching, sym.), 1293 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1253 (C–N stretching in N–C₂H₅, 3°amine), 851 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–NO stretching); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 1.49–1.52 (3H, t, N–CH₂CH₃), 2.11–2.24 (2H, m, N–CH₂CH₃), 3.54–3.59 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.91–3.94 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.51–7.59 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.15–8.26 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 264(100) $[M+1]^+$, 211(25), 192(20), 177(11), 162(18), 141(14), 139(16), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(96), 99(18), 77(21).

5c : Yield : 1.05 g, 68%, m.p. 53–54 °C (Found : C, 57.02; H, 6.76; Cl, 14.01; N, 22.19. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{17}ClN_4$: C, 57.03; H, 6.78; Cl, 14.03; N, 22.17%); UV λ_{max} (ethanol) : 288.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3018 (aromatic C–H stretching), 1591 (N=N stretching), 1550 (C=C ring stretching), 1311 (aromatic C–N stretching), 1188 (C–N stretching, 3°amine), 1095 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–Cl stretching); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 1.02–1.06 (3H, t, N–CH₂CH₃), 2.44–2.52 (2H, m, N–CH₂CH₃), 3.38–3.44 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 3.72–4.04 (4H, m, N–CH₂), 7.35–7.45 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS (ESI) m/z [% rel. abundance] : 253(60) $[M+1]^+$, 254(20) $[M+2]^+$, 11(35), 192(72), 177(31), 162(21), 133(16), 141(14), 122(100), 105(86), 85(100), 113(16), 99(24), 77(51).

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